

2 **Ontology in the Modern Computer Era**

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10 **ABSTRACT**

11 For decades, the concept of ontology has been daunting in literature. Many miscon-
12 ceptions exist regarding its definition. In this paper, these confusions are cleared up.
13 A unified definition or understanding of ontology is established, which also helps
14 to distinguish ontology, work, and work domain. Indeed, prior to the emergence of
15 the computer, ontology is related to physics and philosophy, which does not have
16 much confusion. Now, in the era of modern computers and informatics, ontology is
17 connected to the computer along with the computer’s language or data (information
18 and knowledge), which leads to confusion, as now ontology is across the human and
19 computer. The fundamental reason for the confusion is the lack of understanding of
20 this change, in particular the relationship between ontology and data model. This
21 paper establishes this relationship, which makes it possible to define the so-called
22 data model of ontology (or ontology model for short), and further to define the data
23 model of work and the data model of the work domain. Finally, this paper exam-
24 ines data modelling techniques for ontology modelling, work modelling, and work
25 domain modelling. Throughout this paper, healthcare systems are used to facilitate
26 discussions.

27 **KEYWORDS**

28 Ontology; Healthcare; Data model; Work domain; Ontology modelling

29 **1. Introduction**

30 Ontology is the branch of philosophy that deals with the nature of existence
31 (**Merriam2022**), or a part of philosophy that studies what it means to exist
32 (**Collins2022**). Ontology is thus used to unify people’s view of the physical world
33 – its origin and meaning of existence. Ontology can be said to be a founding stone
34 for the communication between humans and humans in the physical world. The emer-
35 gence of the computer has changed the role of ontology from communication among
36 humans to communication between humans and computers. Such ontology may be
37 coined as computer ontology or data ontology. This paper discusses the data ontology.
38 Without much confusion, throughout this paper, ontology and data ontology are used
39 interchangeably.

40 For decades since the emergence of the computer, there are many
41 understandings and thus definitions of data ontology. For example,

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42 **gruber1993translation**<empty citation> claimed that an ontology is an
43 explicit specification of a conceptualization. Studer et al. (1998) defined on-
44 tology to be a formal, explicit specification of a shared conceptualization.
45 **fernandez2022curie**<empty citation> described ontology as a set of things
46 whose existence is acknowledged by a particular theory or system of thought.
47 In fact, the foregoing definitions much inherit from the original ontology
48 rather than the data ontology. With more attention to the data ontology,
49 **wang2004ontology**<empty citation> referred to ontology as the shared
50 understanding of some domains, which is often conceived as a set of entities, relations,
51 functions, axioms, and instances. **forbes2018ontology**<empty citation> believed
52 that ontology is a knowledge structure, reflecting how humans classify and structure
53 their knowledge of concepts and make logical inferences to reach new understandings.
54 **galton2011ontology**<empty citation> categorizes ontology into three types:
55 reference ontology, domain ontology, and application ontology.

56 It may be clear that different starting points to view ontology do exist after the
57 emergency of the computer: original ontology or data ontology. Yet, even in the data
58 ontology, one can see diverse definitions. Without a unified definition, it is hard to
59 evaluate different products out of diverse understandings and definitions of ontology.
60 This paper attempts to provide a unified understanding and definition of ontology or
61 data ontology. In addition, the data model of ontology is defined in relation to the
62 data model of work and the data model of work domain. Finally, this paper examines
63 data modelling techniques for ontology modelling, work modelling, and work domain
64 modelling. Throughout the paper, healthcare data systems are used for illustration of
65 our idea and for demonstration.

66 2. Common Confusions of Ontology

67 Many studies used ontology in data modelling but confused it with other terms such
68 as work domain model (**cai2017maximum**; **lin2001proposal**; **lin2004towards**).
69 For example, **sanderson2019function**<empty citation> developed the so-called
70 ontology model for an adaptive production system. The ontology model in their study
71 represents a system's function, structure, and behaviour without their relationships.
72 While the definition of the function, structure, and behaviour of a system is consid-
73 ered as work domain modelling in the work of (**cai2017maximum**). In the work of
74 **wang2016domain**<empty citation>, the ontology model was confused with the
75 work domain model. The authors considered the ontology model and work domain
76 model the same and thus use them interchangeably. A similar phenomenon can be
77 found in the work of **singh2021data**<empty citation>, where the so-called ontol-
78 ogy is used to build a work domain model for managing work databases.

79 There is however a common understanding of the role of ontology,
80 i.e., sharing and integration of information within a system. For instance,
81 **fernandez2022curie**<empty citation> proposed a methodology to create an on-
82 tology model that describes the key elements of a system, their characteristics,
83 and the associations among them. The ontology they defined is the data ontology.
84 The main problem with their study is that their definition of the ontology misses
85 the notion of semantics. According to **zhang1994integrated**<empty citation>,
86 semantics is a body of knowledge about the meaning of a symbolic representa-
87 tion that is created based on specific rules (syntactics) and in a specific con-
88 text; the meaning is thus strongly context sensitive. The ontology model in

89 **fernandez2022curie**<empty citation> has not included the notion of context.
90 Consequently, when communicating concepts as well as their relationships to differ-
91 ent parties that are in different contexts, concepts with the same name may mean
92 differently, and relationships among concepts may no longer make any sense.

93 The notion of contexts is not unfamiliar to computer special-
94 ists, though a comprehensive definition of this notion may re-
95 fer to **zhang1994integrated**<empty citation>, **zhang2016design;**
96 **zhang2019integrated**<empty citation>, where to a specific data (an entity
97 or a relationship among entities), a context is a background to contribute to the
98 meaning of data along with the syntax of the data. Unfortunately, there is no study to
99 our best knowledge that explicitly describes the notion of context along with an ontol-
100 ogy model. It is worth mentioning that the context here is different from the context
101 in context-aware computing in the work of **wang2004ontology**<empty citation>
102 and **gu2020ontology**<empty citation>, where computers operate in customized
103 ways in accordance with a specific situation of user activities.

104 3. A Unified Definition of Ontology

105 The data ontology is a common understanding of a subject regardless of different com-
106 puter or data languages, and its role is therefore to facilitate the communication among
107 humans and between the computer and human, and as such to facilitate the integra-
108 tion of data (information and knowledge). The ontology is analogous to a dictionary
109 to the human, a generalized dictionary to the computer in this case. In the human
110 dictionary, there are words along with the meaning of the words and the illustration of
111 the usage of the words. In this generalized dictionary (or dictionary to the computer),
112 there are words and groups of words, among which relationships among words are a
113 special type of groups, constructed by following specific syntactic or grammatic rules.
114 Further, in the generalized dictionary or the ontology, the context is explicitly specified
115 for any word and the relationship among words. It cannot be more emphasized the
116 importance of the notion of context, as it is pivotal to defining the meaning of words
117 and relationships. For example, the word “fan” could be an instrument for producing
118 a current of air in the context of a device. It could also mean an enthusiastic devotee
119 in the context of a sport or an art.

120 The proposed definition of ontology is further built upon five ideas. The **first idea** is
121 that knowledge in nature is an instance. The **second idea** is that information in nature
122 is a class. As previously stated, information is a concept that can be generalized using
123 a set of attributes. On the other hand, knowledge is unique, and it is specific to given
124 concepts. For example, information such as patient and HCP (Healthcare Professional)
125 are classes, that contain attributes such as name, sex, age, etc. Knowledge like how
126 HCPs treat patients is very specific to an individual HCP and patient.

127 The **third idea** is related to the so-called information relativity (IR). The
128 notion of IR was first coined by **zhang1994integrated**<empty citation> and
129 **li2000generalization**<empty citation> in describing a data repository. A data
130 can be taken as a type, an attribute, a class, and an instance, depending on how
131 the data is used. For example, ‘patient’ is viewed as a class, which has an attribute
132 called ‘diagnosis’. However, ‘diagnosis’ could be taken as a class if it represents a set
133 of diagnosis variations or instances.

134 The **fourth idea** is that semantics are determined by context. As knowledge is very
135 specific, a context is necessary to define situations that apply to the knowledge. For

136 example, the knowledge "patients follow advice" should be applied only in the context
137 "patients follow advice from HCPs".

138 The **fifth idea** is that constructs can be instances (knowledge), classes (informa-
139 tion), and relationships. In this connection, **chen1976entity**<empty citation> def-
140 inition of "entity" is expanded. In Chen's work, an instance is defined as a thing that
141 can be distinctly identified. The concept of entity is expanded with the first four ideas
142 above. Based on the notion of IR (the third idea), a class could also be a construct. It
143 depends on using either an element's view or a system's view. Based on the notion of
144 semantics (the fourth idea), a relationship could be a construct as well. For example,
145 the relationship "marriage" can be viewed as an instance under a certain context.

146 4. Data and Data Model

147 Integrating an ever-evolving and heterogeneous set of data sources is a challenging
148 problem, referred to as the data variety challenge (**horrocks2016using**). Traditional
149 data integration techniques are unable to address this problem. A data model of on-
150 tology is one approach to dealing with it. It contributes to addressing the data variety
151 challenge by providing a conceptual view of the data and assisting in the creation of
152 a data model that facilitates data sharing and integration. Therefore, the data model
153 of ontology (or ontology model, for short) becomes a key concept that needs to be
154 defined. Before we discuss the ontology model, the concepts of data and data model
155 should be discussed. According to **zhang1994integrated**<empty citation>, data
156 is a vehicle to carry information and/or knowledge. Information is concepts, e.g., the
157 earth revolves around the sun. It is usually based on observation or interpretation.
158 Knowledge is a causal relation among concepts, e.g., gravitational force causes an ap-
159 ple to fall. Knowledge is usually related to a purpose. For example, to explain why an
160 apple falls.

161 A data model is a language for communication between humans and computers.
162 For the purpose of being understood by computers and by humans, it naturally has
163 two layers: a physical layer and a human layer. The data model at the physical layer is
164 suitable for computers (i.e., the structure of the computer), and the data model at the
165 human layer is suitable for humans, which is close to natural language. The human
166 layer data model is also called semantic data model.

167 A data model has a set of constructs and rules for the constructs
168 (**wang2014integration**; **ter1997comparative**; **yu2021semantic**). For instance, in
169 the Entity-Relationship (E-R) data model (**chen1976entity**; **chen2002entity**), there
170 are three core constructs: (1) Entity, (2) Attribute, and (3) Relationship. One rule is
171 that a relationship connects two entities.

172 5. Ontology Model, Work Model, and Work Domain Model

173 Based on the definitions of ontology and data model, it can also conclude that a data
174 model at the human layer is an ontology. In comparison, a data model at the physical
175 layer is not an ontology, as it doesn't directly facilitate communications between hu-
176 mans. Therefore, we define an ontology model as an ontology of a data model at the
177 human layer. The ontology model provides a set of constructs for humans to describe
178 data (information and knowledge) in a computer system.

179 Under the definition of ontology model, we further define:

- Data model of work is a description of a work using a data model as its language.
- Data model of work domain is a description of the scope of a work by defining its components and variations of those components. An ontology model can be used a language for the description.

The definition of data model of work domain is further explained by the following three understandings.

The first understanding is about the concept of work. Work is a human-machine system. To an automated system, the work is machine. To a human system, the work is human. Under the definition of a data model, such as a healthcare system, the work involves both humans and computers (machines).

The second understanding is about the concept of domain. Domain evolved from the concept of variables. If X is a variable, the domain of X defines its scope or bound, which means that X can only take values that are within the scope or bound. The domain D of X is thus x_1, x_2, \dots . This then comes up with the description of the domain.

The third understanding is about the concept of work domain, which is the information that gives the scope or bounds of the work. In another word, a work has variations. For example, if a thing is a length of bed, say 200 mm, then it has variations from 180 mm to 240 mm. In this case, the domain of the length of the bed is 180–240 mm. In addition, a compound work has multiple primitive things. For example, a bed is a compound work that has primitive things, include length, weight, height, etc. The bed has variations, such as s_1, s_2, \dots , and its primitive things have their own domains, such as the domain of length, the domain of weight, and so on.

The fourth understanding is that a compound work can be decomposed in different ways. For example, when we are investigating a healthcare call center, we can use FCBPSS (Function-Context-Behavior-Principle-State-Structure) (**zhang2016design**) to decompose the work, as shown in Figure 1. The work is decomposed into structure, state, behaviour, etc. The structures are patients, general public, healthcare professionals, and equipment. The states include the physical and mental states. The function is to plan healthcare resources according to demand. The behavior is the casual relationship among physical and mental states of people.

Figure 1. The structures are patients, general public, healthcare professionals and equipment.

211 6. Techniques for Ontology Modelling, Work Modelling, and Work 212 Domain Modelling

213 Based on the requirements outlined in the working definition of ontology, we propose
214 a set of ontology modelling tools as pre-defined constructs. Note that people may refer
215 ontology modelling tools that are presented at the external level, such as modelling
216 languages or editors that create ontology models. In contrast, our tools are on the
217 conceptual level. This makes them very flexible in applications (external level), where
218 it can be incorporated into any existing languages such as OWL (Web Ontology Lan-
219 guage) and used in any editor, such as Protégé (**noy2003protege**). Compared to
220 existing modelling tools, which were formed by evolution and interaction, our tool was
221 developed based on design thinking (**zhang2016design**).

222 Three ontology modelling constructs are proposed: 1) context-of, 2) mono-
223 directional relationship, and 3) bi-directional relationship. The concept map of these
224 blocks is shown in Figure 2 and their semantics and notations are discussed in detail
225 below.

- 226 (1) Context-of: The relation of concepts is constrained by their context. When the
227 context changes, the relation has to change its behavior accordingly, although
228 its concepts may never have changed. For example, in the context that patients
229 have trust in a healthcare system, patients follow their HCP’s advice, as shown in
230 Figure 2. In the other context that patients have lost trust in a healthcare system,
231 patients ignore their HCP’s advice. Diagrammatically, we use a plain association
232 with an unfilled circle at the receiver to denote it. Note that in the existing
233 ontology representation, it is possible to replace context-of with constraints such
234 as range or domain. However, the ontology model becomes more semantic by
235 using an explicit construct as the context-of.
- 236 (2) Mono-directional relationship: Cause-effect relationships are directional relation-
237 ships, such as a child of, take care of. We use a plain association with one arrow
238 pointing at the receiver of the relationship, as shown as HCP belongs to a health-
239 care system in Figure 2.
- 240 (3) Bi-directional relationship: When it comes to presenting bi-directional relation-
241 ships, such as equal to and co-related with, diagrammatically, current ontology
242 approaches use two sets of mono-directional relationships. Such approaches are
243 redundant and implicit. Instead, we use a plain association with arrows at both
244 ends to denote it, as shown patient and HCP collaborating with each other, in
245 Figure 2.

246 The ontology modelling constructs facilitate data integration among structured data
247 and semi-structured data. In a case of integrating doctor advice from two data sources,
248 one can refer to the ontology model in Figure 2 and understand that the advice
249 data must be integrated with the patients’ information, due to the mono-directional
250 construct. In addition, the context-of construct illustrates the necessity of referring to
251 HCP’s data. Using the context-of relationship, advice can be classified by the type of
252 HCP or the healthcare system which they belong to. Regardless of the data, structured
253 or semi-structured, the ontology model determines that patient data and HCP data
254 must be integrated alongside advice data for meaningful data analysis.

Figure 2. An example of ontology model for a healthcare system.

255 **7. Conclusion**

256 This paper presents a working definition of ontology and its corresponding modelling
 257 tool. The purpose of this study is to clarify some of the most common confusions
 258 in ontology-related literature. Our definition of ontology is built on ideas about in-
 259 formation, knowledge, information relativity, and context. Three ontology modelling
 260 constructs are proposed, including context-of, bi-directional relationship, and casual
 261 loop. Those constructs help build a more semantic ontology model compared to exist-
 262 ing languages.

263 Based on our understanding of ontology, data model and domain model, we can
 264 conclude that:

- 265 (1) Ontology is for communication, such as a natural language.
- 266 (2) For direct communication among humans, we use natural language.
- 267 (3) For human communication that involves computers, we need a data model.
- 268 (4) A data model is used to describe the ontology of a work along with its domain
 269 and the work domain covering the work.
- 270 (5) Data models facilitate the integration and analysis of data in the era of big data.
 271 They enable organizations to make informed decisions based on a comprehensive
 272 understanding of available information.
- 273 (6) Domain frameworks such as FCBPSS help to describe a system along with its
 274 domain.

275 The following are the contributions of our paper: (1) provision of a working definition
 276 of ontology, particularly from a relativistic standpoint; (2) elaboration of its distinct
 277 feature; (3) clarification of the definition of data model, and its relationship with
 278 working modelling and domain modelling; and (4) development of a new tool for
 279 modelling it, along with a discussion of the unique feature of this new tool as opposed
 280 to tools such as OWL.

281 In conclusion, the proposed definition of ontology clarifies its scope and applications.
 282 Featuring relativity, context view, and design thinking, the corresponding modelling
 283 tool can describe information and knowledge in a more semantic way.

284 **Author Contributions**

285 W.Lin and W.Zhang conceived of the presented idea and developed the theory.
286 P.Babyn and Y.Yan verified the analytical methods. W.Zhang and P.Babyn super-
287 vised the findings of this work. All authors provided critical feedback and contributed
288 to the final manuscript.

289 **Disclosure statement**

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